

Palm: Versatile Group of Plant Material for Landscape Gardening

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Abstract:- Decorative palms are one of the vital components of tropical, subtropical, or even heat temperate weather landscapes. In colder climates, they may be important interiorscape plants and are regularly a focal point in malls, organizations hubs, homes, road and other public areas. There are 181 genera with around 2,600 species are belonging to the circle of relatives Arecaceae (Palmae). The great botanist Linnaeus, referred to as them “Princes of the vegetable country”. in many historical cultures, fingers are image for such ideas as victory, peace and fertility. whilst, these days it represents image for tropics and vacation spots. The manufacturing of decorative palm is a quite small enterprise, yet pretty famous for people who produce on small acreage or ranchettes. decorative palms are widely used in landscaping for his or her wonderful look, making them maximum economically critical flowers inside the international. The clean cultivation of palms and their pleasant look lead them to first-rate favorites in the garden, enhance indoor air quality and used as reduce foliage in domestic or international marketplace too.

I. INTRODUCTION

An unbranched evergreen tree of tropical and warm regions, with a crown of very lengthy feathered or fan-formed leaves, and usually having vintage leaf scars forming a ordinary sample at the trunk. decorative palms are essential components of tropical, subtropical, and even heat temperate climate landscapes. In less warm climates, they are critical interiorscape vegetation and are regularly a focus in department stores, organizations hubs, buildings, avenue and different public areas. There are 181 genera among which six hundred species are belonging to the own family Arecaceae (Palmae). The great botanist Linnaeus, called them “Princes of the vegetable nation”. in lots of historical cultures, fingers are image for such ideas as victory, peace and fertility. even as, nowadays it represents image for tropics and excursion spots. the first present day species, which includes *Nypa fruticans* and *Acrocomia aculeata*, appeared 94 million years in the past, confirmed by fossil *Nypa* pollen dated to 94 million yr ago. The manufacturing of ornamental palm is a fantastically small enterprise, but pretty famous for people who produce on small acreage or ranchettes. decorative palms are broadly used in landscaping for his or her special look, making them maximum economically essential plants inside the international. The easy cultivation of palms and their

pleasant appearance make them outstanding favorites inside the lawn with purify the indoor air and used as reduce foliage in home or worldwide marketplace too.

The significant majority of palms exist within the tropics. variety is highest in wet, lowland tropical forests, specifically in ecological “hotspots”. In India, Andaman Nicobar island have maximum range of palm species as compare to Western and Japanese Ghats. Madagascar, which has more endemic fingers than the whole continental Africa. Colombia might also have the highest range of palm species in a single usa. it's miles predicted that simplest a hundred thirty palm species develop clearly past the tropics, maximum of which grow inside the subtropics.

II. BOTANY

The flowers are normally small and white, radially symmetric, and can be either uni- or bisexual. The sepals and petals usually in quantity 3 every and can be distinct or joined at the bottom. The stamens usually wide variety six, with filaments that can be separate, connected to every different, or connected to the pistil at the bottom. hands have big, evergreen leaves which can be either palmately ('fan-leaved') or pinnately ('feather-leaved') compound and spirally arranged on the top of the stem. The leaves have a tubular sheath at the bottom that usually splits open on one aspect at adulthood. The inflorescence is a spadix or spike surrounded by means of one or greater bracts or spathes that grow to be woody at adulthood. The flowers are usually small and white, radially symmetric, and can be both uni- or bisexual. The sepals and petals usually quantity 3 each, and may be joined at the base. The stamens commonly number six, with filaments that can be separate, connected to every other, or connected to the pistil at the bottom. The fruit is usually a single-seeded drupe (now and again berry-like) however some genera (e.g., *Saraca*) may incorporate.

Fig1. Morphology of palm regarding its fruits, leaves and bearing habit

- *Why palms are very popular?*
- Its having long, clean, round upright trunk with evergreen crown
- Symmetrical growth, which makes avenue beautiful and discipline
- They have wide range for selection: tall, intermediate, dwarf, sun lover, partial or shade loving, clumping or single stem
- Palms are expensive initially, but in the long run enhance the prestige of properties immensely
- Do not litter fall on ground and dry leaves remain attached
- It requires small ground space for growth
- Root system do not cover the large area and most suitable for narrow space
- It can transplant / relocated at any age
- It requires very less care and attention

III. FAMOUS GARDEN & SOCIETY

- *Palm house, Indian Botanical Garden, Kolkata*
This garden was founded in 1787 by Colonel Robert Kyd, an army officer of the East India Company. The Large Palm House containing rich collection of palms including *Lodoicea maldivica* (the double coconut palm); branching palm (*Hyphaene thebaica*) introduced from Egypt; The century Palm (*Corypha macropoda*).

- *Fig 2 Palm house, Indian Botanical Garden, Kolkata*
- *Kamati Baug, Vadodara*
Sayaji Baug is a garden located in Vadodara, Gujarat, India. It is also known as "Kamati Baug," built by H. H. Maharaja Sayaji Rao Gayakwad (who established it in 1879 over an area of 40 hectares.) - a great visionary ruler of Baroda. This place famous for the first collection of unique branching palm (*Hyphaene thebaica*).

Fig 3 Kamati Baug, Vadodara

- *Palm house, Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew*
The building was completed in 1840 and it was designed by Charles Lanyon and constructed by iron-maker Richard Turner, who later build the Palm House at Kew. A list of palms growing now at Kew include about **125 species**.

Fig 4 Palm house, Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew

- *Nong Nooch Tropical Botanical Garden, Thailand*
The garden opened to the public in **1980**, Nowadays, the garden counts **more than 8,000 species** of palms.

Fig 5 Nong Nooch Tropical Botanical Garden, Thailand

➤ *Market value*

In the market, the tropical palms are perceived as more expensive plant compared with traditional plant. Palm price depend upon species and Trunk girth and height of plant e.g., Fox tail palm trunk girth (9 inch) and Height (12 feet) 1500 Rs/piece (According to nursery man), price of palm also depend on their age. Cut foliage price depend upon the Species e.g., Fishtail palm- 80 Rs/bunch (20 stem/bunch), Table palm- 60 Rs/ bunch (10 stem/bunch) [(Pdhrinath M, Pune florist)].

- *Climatic requirements*
- Ideal temperature: 25°- 35°C
- Relative humidity: >50 %
- pH: 6.0 – 7.5

➤ *Propagation*

Fig 6 Seed Germination

Fig 7 Division of clump

➤ Tissue culture

Tissue culture has been widely used for rapid multiplication of many types of plants. However, palms have generally been difficult to establish in tissue culture. All though techniques for tissue culture developed for commercially important food, oil and medicinal palms such as *B. gasipaes*, *C. nucifera*, *E. guineensis*, *E. edulis*, *P. dactylifera* and *Serenoa repens* used for clonal propagation of superior genotypes. All though tissue culture is not used commercially for propagation of ornamental palms.

➤ Soil

Palm can be grown in wide range of soil type (saline/alkane/acidic) of all the area of world but generally selection depend upon climate *i.e.*, warm or cool and also depend upon soil because wide range available in palm.

- Well aerated, good drainage capacity and water holding capacity
- The preferable potting mix for palms should be good garden soil + coco peat + FYM + sand in 1:1:1 (For pot)

➤ Fertilizer

- For maintaining foliage as fresh and green, the plant needs to feed with liquid manure, oil cake and watering may be alternated with weak ammonium sulphate solution (15g/L of water) once in fifteen days. Top-dressing 8 g N₂O -2 g P₂ O₅-12g K₂O +4 Mg once in year during July-August.

Fig 8 Field production of palm

➤ This method widely follows for the largescale palm production

Decorative hands were commercially grown on a wide range of soil types, but soils should be properly drained to provide ok aeration for root growth and to facilitate harvest during intervals of heavy rainfall. In soils with excessive water retaining capability and high-water desk, planting beds may be raised as much as 30 cm or greater to offer higher drainage and to facilitate digging. A disadvantage of raised beds is reduced stability all through excessive winds. Deep soils are preferred, but fingers have been produced in shallow soils 45–60 cm deep. hands can be planted at densities ranging 1,125–10,000 flora in keeping with hectare, depending at the species grown and the size to which they will be grown. arms in an effort to be mechanically harvested are generally grown with row spacing of 3.00–3.6m to facilitate motion of system, however those so as to be hand dug can be grown in rows spaced as low as 2.4m aside. for optimum use of space, arms may be planted in double rows with vegetation staggered growing a diamond pattern of planting. they will be grown as monocultures or small coloration-tolerant species can be interplanted underneath larger species to optimize the usage of space. fingers may also be interplanted with non-palm trees or shrubs if consideration is given to increase rate, unfold, shade tolerance, and age at advertising and marketing. Liners planted into area nurseries are typically grown in packing containers of 11–19 L. Smaller field-grown hands are less pricey however often result in decrease survival charge. whilst material root-control bags (grow luggage) have been endorsed for branching in non-palm timber grown in subject nurseries, the large diameter of primary palm roots results in wrapping roots in place of a branched root device whilst arms are grown in those bags.

• Irrigation

Irrigation frequency depends on soil water holding capacity, water table, species grown and their age, and rainfall. Those authors suggested that the duration of irrigation be sufficient to wet the soil to a depth of 0.6–0.9 m. Newly planted palms receiving no rainfall may require frequent irrigation in sandy soils during the first 6 months, with irrigation frequency reduced thereafter.

• Fertilization

Fertilizer requirements for field-grown palms vary widely depending on soil type and rainfall. For palms growing in the predominantly sandy soils of the Atlantic Coastal Plain of the south eastern United States, a fertilizer having an analysis of 8N₂O or 2P₂O₅- 12 K₂O- 4 Mg plus micronutrients is recommended for field-grown palms. Use of fertilizers having higher N: K ratios than this have exacerbated K and Mg deficiencies in field-grown palms and even resulted in their deaths.

- *Harvesting (Transplanting)*

The digging and transplanting of field-grown palms destined for landscape use is discussed in the section on Transplanting. Field-grown palms intended for interior usage should be dug with a root ball slightly smaller than the container in which they are to be placed. If they are to be transported out of state, they may need to have their root balls rinsed free of any native soil.

- *Harvesting Leaves for Cut Foliage*

Leaves from palms grown for cut foliage production will be harvested on a regular basis over a period of years. The oldest blemish-free leaves should be selected since, older leaves generally have longer vase lives due to greater carbohydrate reserves than younger leaves. The number of leaves that can be harvested will depend on the species and the interval between harvests, but in general, no more than one-third of the canopy should be removed at any one time.

IV. INTERIORS CAPE MANAGEMENT

- *Palm selection for interiorscape use:*

The best species for interiorscape use are found in the understory of forests where light levels are naturally low. Species from moist, dry, or monsoon forests will likely be more tolerant of low humidity in interiorscapes than species from wet or cloud forests.

- *Soil or planting substrate*

Maximum interiorscape plants are displayed in containers or in specialized planting beds in which the use of a soilless substrate is beneficial. Such substrates need to maintain water and nutrients, yet be porous and properly aerated. Water keeping capacity ought to be 30–40 % and air space ought to be 15–25 %. Generally, such substrates are composed of an organic fraction to offer water and nutrient keeping skills and an inorganic fraction to offer aeration and drainage. Substrates with excessively high quantities of organic components will degrade swiftly, reducing porosity and aeration and cause negative boom.

- *Light*

Light duration is also important. At least 8–12 h of light at or slightly above the LCP per day is recommended for plants in the interiorscape. If natural light is insufficient, supplemental lighting can boost light intensity up to 6.5 klux.

- *Relative humidity*

Relative humidity levels in interiorscapes are generally low, usually below 50 %, but they can drop to as low as 10–20 %, especially during can typically tolerate relative

humidity down to 50% without damage, but at 10 % leaf tip burn can occur

- *Temperature*

Temperatures in interiorscapes, which can range from 20 to 24°C on workdays, are generally suitable for most palms. However, temperatures below 18°C can reduce growth

- *Water*

Excessive irrigation is a common problem in interiorscapes and can lead to root damage, disease, nutritional problems, and other disorders. The root ball, backfill, and surrounding soil of newly planted palms should be kept evenly moist, not saturated.

- *Fertilization*

Because little or no growth occurs or is desired in interiorscapes, nutritional needs of palms are correspondingly low.

V. LANDSCAPE MANAGEMENT

- *Transplanting*

The success or failure of transplanting depends on a number of factors, both above and below ground.

- *Root Ball Size*

The surest root ball length is the smallest root ball that outcomes in a suitable survival fee. but, quantifying that most reliable size has been a piece extra difficult. Root balls want now not be any large than 30 cm from the trunk or 30 cm deep for most species due to the fact the best root density is focused inside this extent. For different species that produce huge numbers of new adventitious roots similarly to reduce root survival, a aggregate of roots derived from both resources ought to be taken into consideration in the equation. because root balls are three-dimensional, root ball intensity should also be considered while figuring out minimal root ball size.

- *Planting*

Planting sites should have suitable drainage, with hard pan layers drilled through for drainage. fingers also can be planted on built up mounds or berms to enhance drainage. negative drainage and/or immoderate irrigation can result in poor status quo rates and subsequent boom. Planting holes should be approximately twice the diameter of the root ball, but no deeper than the root ball. it's far essential to scrub soil down beneath and across the root ball to cast off air pockets because palm roots had been discovered now not to grow into voids inside the soil. Deep planting of large arms has been used to relieve the want for helping transplanted palms and to create plantings of uniform peak when using palms of unequal heights. over the years, deeply planted hands regularly showcase persistent micronutrient deficiencies, stunting, wilting, increased insect pest pressure, and mortality.

- *Leaf Removal and Tying.*

Because water stress is the primary cause of transplant failure in palms, it is a standard practice to remove one-third

to two-thirds of the lower leaves to reduce transpirational water loss. It is necessary for palms transplanted in extremely hot, arid conditions, even if palms are irrigated regularly. Another practice used to reduce transpirational water loss in transplanted palms is tying them into a tight bundle. This is normally done to reduce leaf damage during shipping and handling, but the practice of keeping the leaves tied up for up to 6 months following transplanting has been controversial.

➤ Pruning

Pruning in palm is elimination leaves, inflorescences or someday whole stems. If the palm has a crown shaft, the useless leaf will abscise and fall off evidently (self-cleaning), however in species without crown shafts, the useless leaves might also fall off or they will remain firmly connected till the leaf base finally rots off or is manually removed (non-self-cleaning). It's miles normal for leaf bases or entire leaves of some fingers species to persist for decades or even many years following senescence. Due to the massive length of palm leaves, ok-deficient older leaves are conspicuous and detract from the cultured appearance of the palm, and they're normally eliminated from fingers for the duration of pruning. But, due to the fact k is exceptionally cellular inside palm canopies, those symptomatic older leaves function a supplementary supply of k for the palm within the absence of enough okay inside the soil and as a consequence must now not be eliminated. Pruning, or extra importantly, over pruning, can affect hands in a number of methods. If fingers are over pruned, the reduction in canopy size consequences in reduced photosynthetic potential. In the brief term, a few research have proven that over pruning can result in extra leaf manufacturing prices.

Over pruning palm canopies to only a few leaves have been promoted as a way of lowering wind resistance and enhancing survival of arms throughout hurricanes. The number of leaves that can be eliminated at each pruning is a function of k fame. Because older leaf's function supplemental sources of okay in ok-deficient palms, only completely dead leaves ought to be eliminated. Timing of pruning in hands does no longer appear to be important, although numerous elements can also impact whilst they're pruned in distinct areas. In areas situation to hurricanes or different robust seasonal storms, pruning of dead leaves, inflorescences, and infructescences (particularly coconuts) simply prior to the windstorm season can be most excellent. In areas wherein bloodless damage may want to arise, pruning before the wintry weather months need to be averted on bloodless-sensitive hands as a full canopy presents more insulation than an overpruned one.

➤ Effect of plant growth regulators

Plant boom regulators play a first-rate position to manipulate palm top, flowering, suckering and rooting. Seeds of several species of palms had been soaked in GA₃, the resulting seedlings exhibited excessively elongated or even twisted boom in the course of their first 12 months. Most species, leaves emerging treatment with gibberellic acid (GA₃) assumed a extra juvenile form, with leaflets failing to break up usually. Boom retardant consisting of daminozide or chlormequat had no effect on length or form of leaves or on

suckering in *Chamaedorea seifrizii*, *Caryota mitis* or *Dypsis lutescens*, however chlormequat darkened the inexperienced coloration of the leaves in all species and leaf size became reduced in all of those species through ethephon.

➤ Indoor air quality improve by palm

In urbanized population, people spending 80-90 % of their time indoors. Since many people spend much of their time indoors, long-term exposure to VOCs in the indoor environment can contribute to sick building syndrome. Concentrations of VOCs are higher in indoors than outdoors. Indoor plants are effective at removing VOCs.

➤ Impact of pollution on growth of palm

Air pollution have a poor effect on boom of palms, frequently via interfering with aid accumulation. Airborne sulfur dioxide (SO₂) has been proven to reason red- orange necrosis parallel to the veins and leaflet margins in *Dypsis lutescens* leaves. Leaflet of hands uncovered to fluoride show necrotic lesions, sally arranged in parallel rows alongside the longitudinal axis.

➤ Some research work done on palms

The survey of south Gujarat region on diversity of palm in Surat district and total 33 species of palm were recoded among them, five were cultivated and remains in wild and ornamental form [6]. Maximum seed germination (79.40 %) and seed germination index (1.2190) of Queen Palm (*Syagrus romanzoffiana*) at 30°C temperature in control environmental condition of Brazil [5]. Maximum plant height and stem diameter were observed through the foliar fertilizer application of NPK @ 8:9:9 compared to granular application of NPK@ 10:10:10 in lady palm seedling [4]. *Chamaedorea elegans* grown in greenhouse resulted maximum plant height (56.76 cm), number of leaves per plant (7.06), stem diameter (16.17 cm) as well as fresh weight (42.64 g) and dry weight (21.19 g) of shoots [1]. Transplanting of old pygmy date palms at the original depth or up to the top of the visible portion of the root initiation zone (0 cm to 15 cm) resulted optimum survival with good plant quality [2]. Bamboo palm (*Chamaedorea seiterzii*) removed highest amount of benzene (34,073 µg) and formaldehyde (76,707 µg) through maximum leaf surface area (10,325 cm²) from a sealed experimental chamber during 24 hr exposure period [8]. GA₃ (50 ppm) + BA (20 ppm) + 8- HQC (300 ppm) + CA (300 ppm) + Sugar (2 %) significantly increased the vase life (84.00 days) and dry weight (1.63 g) of *Chamaedorea elegans* with higher general appearing score (4.0) [7]. Wax coating @ 0.5 % of fishtail palm (*Caryota urens*) leaf had maximum useful vaselife and total vaselife [3].

VI. CONCLUSION

From the forgoing dialogue, it is able to be concluded that palm is maximum flexible and thrilling institution of plant and provide the highest esteem by using garden armature with wide variety of selection in special panorama viz. tropical, rainforest, barren region as well as sea shore vicinity. Better germination potential of palm seed can be performed at 30 °C temperature. Media in combination of

compost + peat moss + perlite located promising for higher boom and improvement of pot plant. green residence circumstance could be very a whole lot suitable for commercial cultivation of pleasant cut foliage manufacturing. Foliar feeding via NPK @ 8:9:9 and NPK every @ 4g / plant profound for higher growth of palm seedling and pot plant. Transplanting of old palm at the intensity from seen portion of the basis initiation area (zero cm to 15 cm) executed better survive charge. yearly drenching of Paclobutrazol @ 1.6 g a.i. observed effective for lessen the vertical boom in landscaping. positive palm species have the capacity to take away benzene, Formaldehyde and certain VOCs from the indoor air and purify it. Areca palm, Fish tail palm and Bamboo palm can also be cultivated commercially for cut foliage functions and vase life can be improved through GA3 (50 ppm) + BA (20 ppm) + eight- HQC (three hundred ppm) + CA (300 ppm) + Sugar (2 %) or wax coating @ 0.5 % remedy. moreover, waste of palm species mainly coir dirt, dry leaves and husk of end result can also utilize for soil moisture conservation.

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